

Adsorptive detection of ethoxyquin on multi-walled carbon nanotube modified glassy carbon electrode

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Abstract : Ethoxyquin (EQ) is a common preservative used in several animal feeds such as fish, poultry and dairy food products. Excess addition of the EQ, (>75 ppm) to food products led to several health problems. Different analytical methods have been proposed for the determination of EQ in food samples. Unfortunately, existing methods are complicated and expensive. Here in, we report a selective and non enzymatic electro-analytical assay based on a multi-walled carbon nanotube modified glassy carbon electrode (GCE/MWCNT) with pH 7 of 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution for EQ analysis. A dilute ethanolic solution of EQ adsorbed GCE/MWCNT, i.e. GCE/MWCNT@EQ showed well-defined surface confined redox peak at -0.2 V vs Ag/AgCl, which is due to formation of a quinoline derivative on the interface. The peak potential and current values were taken as specific tool for the EQ quantification assays. Repeated experiment on unmodified GCE failed to show any such defined redox peak. The developed chemically modified electrode (CME) was characterized by Raman spectroscopy and FT-IR.

Keywords : Ethoxyquin, multi-walled carbon nanotube, chemically modified electrode, electrochemical sensor.

Introduction

Ethoxyquin (EQ, 6-ethoxy-1,2-dihydro-2,2,4-trimethylquinoline) is widely used in for the protection of lipid peroxidation in animal feeds¹. It is also added in other food items like poultry², edible oils³, vegetables especially apple and pears⁴ as a preservative. Through food chain contamination the EQ enter in to the human physiological system. EQ can cause many unfavorable side-effects, skin allergies, weight loss, increase in the mass of liver and kidney and accumulation of lipids in kidney etc. Hence, sensitive, fast and accurate analytical methods are highly needed to detect the EQ in the food samples.

Common analytical methods used for the detection of EQ are; gas chromatography (GC), high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled UV absorbance or fluorescence⁵, liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) and time-of-flight mass spectrometry LC-TOFMS⁶. Although these methods are sensitive but require fairly long time and tedious working sample preparation procedures along with toxic, high pure and

expensive solvents such as pyridine, methanol, toluene and lithium perchlorate. Alternatively, electrochemical methods offer simple, high sensitivity, selectivity and relatively less time and low cost. Unfortunately, there is no specific electrochemical report available for EQ. For the first time in literature, a pristine multi-walled carbon nanotube chemically modified electrode (GCE/MWCNT) is used as analytical tool for the selective detection of EQ, in this work. Recently, carbon nanotube materials have attracted tremendous interest in electroanalytical chemistry owing to its good electrical conductivity, appreciable chemical stability and extremely high mechanical strength⁷⁻⁹. Utilizing the GCE/MWCNT, several organic and pharmaceutical compounds such as phenol, catechol, amoxicillin, tetracycline, alpha-naphthol, anthracene, and pyrene were successfully electro-oxidized to quinone species as surface confined electrochemical systems and further to various electro-analytical applications. In this work, GCE/MWCNT was used as an electrochemical substrate for EQ adsorption and further to voltammetric sensing.

Experimental

Ethoxyquin and MWCNTs (>90% carbon basis, outer diameter : 10–15 nm; inner diameter : 2–6 nm; length 0.1–10 μm) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (USA). All the other chemicals used in this work were of ACS-certified reagent grade and used without further purification. Aqueous solutions were prepared using deionized and alkaline KMnO_4 distilled water. Unless otherwise stated pH 7 phosphate buffer (PB) solution of 0.1 M ionic strength was used as a supporting electrolyte.

Voltammetric measurements were all carried out with a CHI Model 660C electrochemical workstation (USA). The three-electrode system consisted of glassy carbon or its carbon nanotubes chemically modified form as a working electrode (0.0707 cm^2), Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) as a reference electrode and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode. GCE (Bioanalytical system, USA) was cleaned both mechanically (polished with 0.5 μm alumina powder, cleaned with acetone and washed with DD water) and electrochemically (by performing cyclic voltammetry (CV) for 10 cycles in a potential window -0.2 to 1.0 V vs Ag/AgCl at a potential scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} in pH 7 PB solution). A stock solution containing MWCNT/ethanol was prepared by dissolving 1 mg of MWCNT in 500 μL of ethanol and sonicated for ~ 5 min at room temperature (25 ± 1 $^\circ\text{C}$). The GCE/MWCNT was prepared by drop casting 5 μL of the above stock solution on the electrode surface, followed by 15–20 min drying at room temperature.

Results and discussion

Initially, a EQ adsorbed glassy carbon electrode (GCE/

EQ), which was prepared by drop casting of 10 μL of a stock solution containing 25 mg EQ dissolved in 500 μL , was potential cycled in a window, -0.5 to 0.5 V versus Ag/AgCl in pH 7 PB solution by cyclic voltammetry technique. As can be seen in Fig. 1 curve a, no faradic response was noticed in the above case. This observation implies unreactive feature of the EQ on the conventional carbon electrode. Interestingly, when the above experiment is repeated on MWCNT-modified GCE electrode (GCE/MWCNT@EQ), which has been prepared by the successive drop casting of 5 μL of 2 mg/mL MWCNT/ethanol and the EQ solution, dried in air followed by continuous cyclic voltammetry, showed a profound growth of a new redox peak centered equilibrium potential of $E_{1/2} = -115 \pm 5$ mV versus Ag/AgCl (Fig. 1b). The redox peak increases its current magnitude upon increasing CV cycling number upto 60. After the experiment, the above working electrode was gently washed with DD water, medium transferred to a blank consisting of pH 7 PBS and done CV again. The redox peak is retained without any marked alteration in the peak potential and current (Fig. 1c). Further we calculated the surface excess of EQ (Γ_{EQ}) by using equation : $\Gamma_{\text{EQ}} = q/nFA$ (n = no. of electrons; F = Faraday constant and A = area of the electrode), which yielded a value 0.875 n mol cm^{-2} . These above observations attribute electro-assisted adsorption of the EQ, as a surface confined redox species, on the MWCNT surface. It is expected that the EQ gets oxidized as quinoline derivative upon continuous CV cycling and showed redox peak. The pi-pi interaction between MWCNT and EQ is a key for the selective adsorption and ET (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Illustration for the electrochemical oxidation and modification of EQ to quinoline derivative on MWCNT electrode surface.

The chemically modified electrode is further subjected to various physicochemical and electrochemical characterizations. The results are given below :

carbons on the surface¹⁰ (i.e. EQ).

Effect of scan rate (ν) on the CV of GCE/MWCNT@EQ was investigated. The experiment shows

Fig. 1. (A) Comparative CV responses of modified electrodes : (a) GCE/MWCNT, (b) GCE/MWCNT@EQ (e-cycling), (c) GCE/MWCNT@EQ (stability) and (d) GCE/EQ at a scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} in pH 7 PBS (electrochemically prepared). (B) FT-IR responses of (a) MWCNT and (b) MWCNT@EQ modified electrodes. (C) Raman spectra of (a) MWCNT and (b) MWCNT@EQ response with calculated I_D/I_G values.

Fig. 1B, FTIR of MWCNT@EQ in comparison with MWCNT showed two specific peaks at 3471 and 1085 cm^{-1} corresponds to O-H and C-O stretching frequencies on the hybrid system. Apart from that, MWCNT@EQ hybrid showed a peak at 1681 cm^{-1} corresponds to the $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ indicating the formation of quinoline derivative on MWCNT@EQ. As shown in Fig. 1C, Raman spectra of MWCNT before and after modification with EQ showed a specific increment in the peak intensity ratio (I) of the disordered graphitic (D) and regular graphitic (G) band (I_D/I_G) from 0.41 to 0.44 , which is due to addition of sp^3

a systematic increase in the peak current response against the ν increase (Fig. 2A). Double logarithmic plot of $\log(i/\mu\text{A})$ vs $\log(\nu/\text{mV s}^{-1})$ of scan rate yielded linear line with a slope on anodic side 0.77 and cathodic side 0.7 . This values reminiscent mixed adsorption-diffusion controlled ET of the EQ on the hybrid film. In continuation, effect of EQ adsorbed concentration ($0.5, 4, 6, 10, 30$ and 50 ppm) on GCE/MWCNT at a fixed scan rate ($\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$) was also investigated (Fig. 2B). Base-line corrected anodic peak current (i_{pa}) increases against increase in EQ concentration. Plot of i_{pa} vs $[\text{EQ}]$ is linear

Fig. 2. (A) Effect of scan rate on GCE/MWCNT@EQ at $\nu = 10\text{--}500 \text{ mV/s}$ in pH 7 PBS, (B) CV responses of different concentrations of EQ modified electrodes at $\nu=50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ in pH 7 PBS and (C) plot of pH vs E_{pa} .

with a slope and regression value $0.655 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{A/ppm}$ and 0.9633 respectively. These results evident the applicability of the present protocol to EQ quantification assays. The MWCNT@EQ modified electrode is pH dependent; altering the solution pH results in peak shift. A plot of peak potential vs solution pH yielded a linear line with a slope ($\partial E_{\text{pa}}/\partial\text{pH} = -67 \text{ mV/pH}$; Fig. 2C). This electrode can be extended further for EQ analysis in various real samples.

Conclusion

Ethoxyquin adsorbed MWCNT-modified glassy carbon electrode showed well-defined and highly sensitive surface-confined redox at -115 V vs Ag/AgCl in pH 7 PB solution, unlike to nil response on unmodified GCE surface. Physiochemical characterization of MWCNT@EQ by FTIR and Raman spectroscopic techniques imply immobilization of EQ as quinoline derivative on MWCNT. The surface-confined redox peak was linear against adsorbed EQ concentration.

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